

ProCleanLakes

Readme file

20250211-ProCleanLakes-D3.1-V4

**Funded by
the European Union**

Project: 101157886 | HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01-04 | www.procleanlakes.eu

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Reason(s) for data analysis: The data was collected within project ProCleanLakes which explores the perceptions of aspiring entrepreneurs and business owners from Norway, Romania, and Greece regarding starting, respectively developing businesses in lake protection and restoration.

Creation date of file(s): 02/2025

Used method(s):

- Survey among 150 aspiring entrepreneurs.
- Survey among 45 business owners from Norway, Romania, and Greece, where demo sites are located.
- Three interviews with business owners from the demo sites.

Used software (incl. version and add-ons) and tools:

- Microsoft Excel
- Prolific platform <https://www.prolific.com/>

Data:

- 20250220_Questionnaire for aspiring entrepreneurs (150 responses)
 - Anonymized dataset of the survey
- 20250220_Questionnaire for business owners (45 responses)
 - Anonymized dataset of the survey

Code:

- 20250211-ProCleanLakes-D3.1-V3

Additional files:

- Questionnaires for both surveys and interview guidelines are attached as annexes 1-3 to the document 20250211-ProCleanLakes-D3.1-V3

License:

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Notes:

- Non-anonymized data is available from the creator for secondary analysis.